

Considering the role of ultraviolet rays in producing melanoma by using concepts of quantum electromagnetic holes

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Abstract: Ultraviolet rays could pass the nuclear membranes, interact with DNAs, RNAs and proteins and cause to stop their activities. We will show that these waves could image DNA bases as some holes within the liquid within the nucleus. These electromagnetic holes could be replicated by polymerases and produce new DNAs. This causes that process of formation of new cells becomes different from known methods and some new cells are emerged which could be the origin of melanoma and cancer.

Keywords: Ultraviolet Ray; Melanoma; Quantum; Electromagnetic hole

I. Introduction

Up to date, the relation between melanoma and ultraviolet rays has been considered extensively. For example, some authors have discussed that uveal melanoma (UM) is the most common intraocular tumour in adults and despite surgical or radiation treatment of primary tumours, ~50% of patients progress to metastatic disease. They have shown that whole genome landscapes of uveal melanoma show an ultraviolet radiation signature in iris tumours [1]. Another authors have discussed about age-dependent interaction between sex and geographic ultraviolet index in melanoma risk. They have shown that the interaction between sex and UVI is age dependent. Female sex is an independent risk factor for early-onset melanoma, but female sex also protects against UV-associated melanoma in older age groups [2]. In other work, authors have estimated the current and future burden of melanoma attributable to ultraviolet radiation in Canada [3]. In another research, authors have classified melanomas by mutation signatures and identify ten recurrently mutated UVR signature genes that predict patient survival. They have validated these findings in primary human melanomas [4]. In another paper, authors have argued that comparisons of skin cancer data from Norway and Australia/New Zealand indicate that squamous cell

carcinoma and basal cell carcinoma are mainly related to annual solar UVB fluences, while UVA fluences play a larger role for CMM [5]. Motivated by these researches, we explore a new mechanism for inducing cancer in skin by ultraviolet rays.

II. Theoretical model:

Fig 1: A new mechanism for inducing extra DNAs by ultraviolet rays

When ultraviolet rays achieve to cellular gates, act like photos of camera. It means that they collide with DNA bases and other matters within the cell. Then, they take shape of DNA bases and are reflect on the liquids within the cells. These waves have huge energies and force on the liquid molecules to take their shapes. In fact, some electromagnetic holes are emerged within the liquid around DNAs. Liquids within cells have many charged particles and they are attracted by electromagnetic waves. Thus, holes are formed by charged particles. Also, some polymerases are attracted by electromagnetic holes and build some real bases from DNA photos. These bases join to each other and form some new genetic matters like RNAs and

DNAs within the cell. These extra biological objects can be covered by some nuclear and cellular membranes and form new cells. These cells could cause to cancer.

III. The relation between melanoma and wavelength

When size of waves becomes smaller than the size of cells, they could penetrate into cells. The size of melanocytes is around 7 micron. We can assume that there is below relation between wavelengths, sizes of cells and the probability for tunneling waves through cell membranes:

$$P = \text{EXP}(-\text{WAVELENGTH}/\text{SIZE OF CELLS})$$

Using above equation and putting 7 micron for the size of melanocytes, we can achieve to below plot. It is clear that by decreasing wavelengths in compared with the size of cells, they could pass the cell membranes and produce different types of diseases. Ultraviolet rays have smaller size than melanocytes and thus, they could enter into the nucleus and produce melanoma and other diseases.

Fig 2: The probability for penetrating waves into melanocytes

Conclusions:

In this paper, we have shown that ultraviolet rays could act like photos of a camera. This means that they could take photos of DNA bases and draw them as electromagnetic holes on the liquid around DNAs. These holes could be replicated by polymerases and produce real bases. These bases could join to each other and form new DNAs. These DNAs could be the origin of melanoma and other cancers.

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